

Reluctance to Consider the Diagnosis of DID, Leading to an Incomplete and Misdiagnosis of the Disorder, Preventing Effective Treatment

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Abstract

The combination of inadequate training in recognizing traumatic dissociation, limited exposure to correct scientific information about IPD, symptom similarities with other disorders (such as schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and borderline personality disorder), and discussion of etiology has led to reluctance to consider the diagnosis of DID, leading to an incomplete and misdiagnosis of the disorder. hindered effective treatment. Reference Reinders , Marquand , Schlumpf , Chalavi , Vissia and Nijenhuis 5 From the time they seek treatment for symptoms to the moment DID is

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correctly diagnosed, individuals on average have four other prediagnoses, inadequate pharmacological treatments, few hospitalizations, and ultimately extended periods in mental health services. they spend years. These years of misdirected treatment cause prolonged personal suffering and high direct and indirect societal costs. Other causes are unfamiliarity with the spectrum of dissociative disorders, the presence of false DID , the reluctance of individuals with DID to present their dissociative symptoms , often because of feelings of shame, and a lack of knowledge and appreciation of its epidemiology. (“Dissociative identity disorder: out of the shadows at last?”) Factors contributing to the underdiagnosis and misdiagnosis of dissociative identity disorder (DID). The lifetime prevalence of DID is estimated to be about 1.5%, Reference. Reinders , Marquand , Schlumpf , Chalavi , Vissia and Nijenhuis⁵ mean that at least one million people in the UK will suffer from DID in their lifetime . (“Dsm v dissociative identity disorder pdf”) It is therefore clinically extremely important to bring DID out of the shadows to ease earlier correct diagnosis, avoid unnecessary suffering, and encourage research into faster and more targeted interventions . of the DKB Evidence from brain biology supporting the trauma theory According to criteria set out in DSM-5, dissociative identity disorder (DID) is characterized by fluctuating consciousness as well as two or more distinct identities or overlapping personality states.

Keywords: *DID, DID, EMDR, Treatment of Dissociative Disorders, Dissociative Disorders, Dissociative Personality Disorder*

1. Introduction

The first evidence of personality state-related brain activity was discovered in a single patient at rest in 1985. This finding has now been confirmed by several other investigations over time. The first multi-participant stimulus-driven neuroimaging study was conducted in 2003 and showed that the processing of neutral and trauma-related autobiographical memory scenarios is dependent on the participant's personality state. Dissociative identity disorder (DID), a controversial psychiatric diagnosis, was first included in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM)

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(DSM-III) in 1980 under the name "multiple personality disorder" . A debate over what causes the disease is at the center of the controversy that has ensued. For decades, proponents of two completely contradictory viewpoints have been in a heated debate. On the other hand, fantasy-model dissociative identity disorder is primarily open to suggestion and enactment and is eased by an elevated level of fantasy disposition and suggestibility. According to the trauma model, dissociative identity disorder is a severe form of post- traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) that results from severe and chronic (childhood) traumatization . Despite the progress of the trauma versus fantasy debate and the scope of etiological research expanding over the past few decades, there are several reasons why the fantasy model continues to appeal to therapists . These reasons are cited in Dorahy and Krüger . Some of the reasons why the information about trauma and dissociation given in undergraduate and graduate textbooks is insufficient or incorrect.

- (a) mostly based on experimental research in non-clinical samples,*
- (b) entirely based on scientific research,*
- (c) childhood traumas and*
- (d) It does not consider empirical evidence of an association between dissociation and prior trauma .*

Such an explanation is a resistance to accepting the extent and intensity of childhood trauma that people with IPD describe as they experience. It is distressing and painful to face the reality of how pervasive and devastating trauma is, especially with repeated abusive behavior in childhood. It is possible that unconscious defense mechanisms kick in and begin to deny the reality of the abuse (just as some people deny the Holocaust, racism or climate change). It is possible to think of dissociative identity disorder (DID) as an artificial condition (see Dalenberg , Brand , Loewenstein , Frewen and Spiegel³) and to do this according to the fantasy model. However, it is becoming increasingly clear that serious childhood abuse, neglect, and maltreatment are part of many psychiatric disorders and our society. In a follow-up study, it was shown that individuals with DID can be distinguished from healthy controls simulating DID by high and low levels of fantasy propensity. (“Dissociative Identity Disorder (DID) — Does it really exist?”) More importantly, these simulation -independent changes in brain activity patterns in different personality states in

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DID were replicated in an independent group and completely invalidated the dream hypothesis for DID. In the DSM-5, a dissociative subtype was added for PTSD and dissociative disorders were placed at once after trauma and stress-related disorders. This placement was made to suggest a close link between dissociative PTSD and dissociative identity disorder (DID).

The research showed similarities in patterns of brain activity during emotion overmodulation and undermodulation in an indirect comparison between the two. These neurobiological similarities between personality states in the ICD and PTSD subtypes support a traumatic event as a possible cause of dissociative identity disorder (DID). In terms of neurostructural evidence, a reduced hippocampal volume is the neuroanatomical correlate of the most often reported childhood traumatization .

childhood abuse and hippocampal volume have been documented transdiagnostically in both drug-naive individuals from the general population and people with mental illness. Chalavi and colleagues referenced Chalavi, Vissia, Giesen, Nijenhuis, Draijer , and Cole⁶ to examine hippocampal global and subfield volumes in PTSD and DBP in relation to childhood traumas to directly evaluate the trauma model for DID . They found that patients with PTSD had larger hippocampal global and subfield volumes than patients with DID. They found a negative correlation between hippocampal volumes and childhood traumatization in the two disorders ; this provided neuroanatomical evidence for clinical observations that DID is associated with (severe) childhood trauma.

The findings were published in the journal *Neuropsychopharmacology* . This finding is particularly important because neuroanatomical data are unlikely to be sensitive to cognitive manipulation . Therefore, these data support the view that IPD is strongly associated with PTSD, as suggested by its place in the DSM-5 , especially when it comes to childhood trauma . supplies evidence for the trauma model. The conclusion that DID is linked to environmental conditions was further strengthened by a multicenter study examining the neurodevelopmental roots of abnormal brain morphology in DID . This research evaluated total cortical volume and its two components, cortical thickness and surface area, in people with DID . He discovered that people with DID differ

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from controls on all three measures and supplied evidence that non-genetic, environmental variables affect various areas of brain development in DID .

2. Early Childhood Traumatic Experiences with Brain Morphology

It has also been shown that there are negative links between abnormal brain morphology and early childhood traumatic experiences. Research on brain activation has shown that, taken as a whole, the DSM-5 identity criterion for dissociative identity disorder (DID) is met by the presence of two or more distinct personality states, each with its own unique pattern. This allowed validation of the DSM-5 authentication criteria for DID. Research on brain morphology in people with dissociative identity disorder has revealed that the condition is not likely to be a neurodevelopmental disorder, but environmental factors such as early childhood traumatization have an impact on brain morphology in people with this disorder.

etiology of dissociative identity disorder (DID) has been debated for decades and DID has It casts doubt on its usefulness as a diagnostic entity in the DSM . Given that neurobiological and other evidence supports the trauma model for IPD, it is unclear why the etiology of dissociative identity disorder (DID) stays controversial (Reference: ar, Dorahy , and Krüger). This is because the etiology of most major psychiatric disorders such as psychosis is also poorly known, but this lack of knowledge does not have such a negative impact on diagnostic detection and treatment. Building on the neurobiological evidence currently available, it's time to pull dissociative identity disorder (DID) out of the shadows and see it as a mainstream psychiatric disorder. By using the variety of national and international educational information and educational opportunities currently available, clinicians can gain a better understanding of dissociation, dissociative symptoms , DID, and dissociative disorders in general.

Some alternative identities first ignore or reject earlier traumatic events and/or their associated effects when they first begin therapy . It is a fundamental part of treatment that these identities gradually embrace the memories and emotions they deny , while accepting the role and importance of other identities that hold them. The acceptance process can be aided by the therapist 's aid in

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forming internal agreements by various alternative identities. The therapist can ease the acceptance process by helping alternative identities come to terms with themselves.

Clinicians must accept the fact that effective treatment of dissociative identity disorder almost always involves relating to and talking to the patient's many personalities. Ignoring different identities or instructing them to automatically "turn inside" is quite obviously counterproductive to the therapeutic process. Early in the therapy process, therapists and patients need to develop techniques for relating to different identities that are both secure and in control. This will ultimately lead to shared consciousness, shared acceptance, and deeper integration. Clinicians have the choice of directly or indirectly reaching out to different people to do their work. Clinicians with years of experience build a toolbox full of capabilities that allow them to access other identities in a more devious way. For example, the clinician might suggest that the patient "listen inside" to hear what other identities are saying, or ask the patient to "listen to himself," so that the clinician may suggest that the identities have internal conversations with themselves. Therapist may "speak to each other" to interact with different identities important to current therapeutic challenges or may insist on "listening to all who need to know" when dealing with vital issues.

More in-depth discussions of therapeutic strategies for accessing and working with alternative identities Putnam (1989), Ross (1997), RP Kluft (2001, 2006), RP Kluft and Fine (1993) and Van der Hart et al. (2006). All these authors are quoted in the earlier sentence. Most hospital stays are quite short and are primarily conducted for the sake of safety, crisis management and stability due to limits imposed by third parties who pay. In some cases, the stability and organization provided by a hospital setting is better suited to support therapeutic work that may be difficult or uncomfortable to conduct in an outpatient setting. Inpatient treatment may include planned and vigilant working on traumatic memories, as well as working with other violent and self-destructive identities and associated behaviors when resources are available to support a longer stay. Specialized inpatient centers dedicated to the treatment of traumatic experiences and/or dissociative disorders can be particularly beneficial when it comes to helping patients develop the skills necessary to be more confident and stable. A general hospital's psychiatry programs typically do not offer the following services: specialized diagnostic evaluations; intensive individual

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psychotherapy; private group therapies; specialist psychopharmacological interventions; and specific trauma-focused work on symptom management and skill development.

3. Aggressive Behaviors Towards Others

aggressive behavior towards himself or others during inpatient treatment and the patient is not responding to verbal, behavioral, or pharmacological therapies, isolation and physical or chemical restraints may be necessary to control the patient's behavior. Unfortunately, closure and restraint have the potential to be traumatic experiences for any patient, especially those who are already suffering from post- traumatic psychopathologies, which should also be considered. As a result, a considerable number of healthcare facilities are now working towards the ideal goal of reducing or cutting the use of isolation and restraint altogether. In this sense, these restrictive measures can often be avoided if careful planning is made in advance for symptom management and control methods. This preparation can be helpful in times of crisis. Patients admitted to some hospital systems are asked to create so-called "personal safety plans."

These plans include situations that have the potential to improve or hinder patients' ability to keep themselves safe. In the case of individuals suffering from DID , they can include naming unique post- traumatic triggers as well as actions that give calming and relaxing effects . Specific therapies for patients with DID may include communicating with helpful alternative identities, using imagery to find an internal "safe space" for overwhelmed or self-harming alternative identities, and using images to "voice" or otherwise mitigate strong effects.

Using so-called "voluntary" physical restraints to have a violent alternate personality while dealing with the effects of trauma is no longer seen as a practical solution. Partial Hospital or Inpatient Care Patients suffering from DID may benefit in some way from general partial hospital programs that serve as an intermediate step between inpatient and outpatient care. The most effective programs for this purpose are likely to be those that allow the survivor to have a specific focus and are aware of the challenges associated with the trauma . Patients with dissociative identity disorder (DID) and others who have been severely traumatized can benefit greatly from either a step up

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from inpatient treatment or avoiding inpatient hospitalization and/or a specialized partial hospital or inpatient treatment as a more intensive outpatient treatment. Overall, these specialty programs educate participants on trauma -related illnesses, provide strategies for symptom management, and provide education in relationships and other life skills with the use of multiple groups each day. It may be possible in these programs to incorporate DDT or other more formally structured and organized approaches to symptom management. Unfortunately, only a small fraction of these specialization programs is currently available to participants.

4. Group Psychotherapy

Patients suffering from DID often perform poorly in generic treatment groups because these groups consist of people with a variety of different diagnoses and clinical problems. Traditional process-focused psychotherapy groups, or groups that allow limited discussion of individuals' traumatic experiences, can cause strong emotions that many people with dissociative identity disorder (DID) find difficult to tolerate. Some of these treatment groups have led to worsening of symptoms or having group members develop problematic relationships with each other. When it comes to ICD treatment, group psychotherapy is not a practical mainstream treatment choice. However, for certain individuals with dissociative identity disorder (DID) or complicated post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), some time-limited group forms may be useful additions to individual therapy. Such groups can help educate patients about trauma and dissociation, help develop specific skill sets (such as coping strategies, social skills, and symptom management), and help patients understand that they are not alone in dealing with dissociative symptoms. traumatic memories Patients may also learn that there are other people who have experienced the same things as them. Groups for this task need to have a time constraint, an elevated level of organization, and a clear concentration on the subject at hand . Some physicians have seen that carefully selected DID patients may receive help from longer-term, homogeneous, more process-oriented groups for DID and complicated PTSD patients. These groups are designed specifically for individuals with DID . For such a group to be successful, there must be a clear therapeutic framework that outlines

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expectations and boundaries for participants' behavior in and out of the group (e.g., limitations in discussing trauma memories within the group, no socialization among members outside the group).

When it comes to dealing with drug abuse issues, some patients may receive help from attending 12-step meetings hosted by organizations such as Alcoholics, Narcotics or Al-Anon. However, 12-step "incest survivor" groups or "self-help" groups that are not led by a trained professional are generally considered contraindicated for DID sufferers. This is because the typical format of these groups is irregular, which can lead to emotional outbursts and other forms of psychological distress. In addition, group members are likely to engage in unhealthy behaviors for themselves and others, such as being uncomfortable, overly dependent, or exploitative. Patients diagnosed with DID who insist on joining such groups are often turned away by professional therapists who would otherwise treat them.

5. Pharmacotherapy

The main treatment for dissociative processes does not include the use of psychotropic drugs, and definitive recommendations for pharmacotherapy for most dissociative symptoms await the completion of a comprehensive study. However, according to reports by therapists, most DID patients were also given medication as part of their therapy (Putnam & Loewenstein, 1993). Eighty percent of patients undergoing outpatient treatment for dissociative disorders were given adjunctive medication, according to the only naturalistic study of such treatment (Brand, Classen, Lanius, et al., 2009). Patients diagnosed with dissociative disorder often receive pharmacotherapy that focuses on the treatment of the hyperarousal and intrusive symptoms of PTSD, as well as co-occurring problems such as mood disorders and obsessive-compulsive symptoms, among other conditions (Loewenstein, 1991b; Torem, 1996). Understanding that the prescription is mostly empirical in nature should be part of the informed consent process when it comes to medication guidelines for DID. To avoid "splitting" the treatment team, psychopharmacological management of ICD requires attention to boundaries and active lines of communication between treating therapists, nonpsychiatric treatment team members, and the

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medicating psychiatrist (especially when the psychiatrist is not also the primary therapist). (“Guidelines For Treating Dissociative IDENTITY DISORDER in ADULTS”) A precise definition of the roles of the therapist and the prescribing psychiatrist is extremely important. During the patient's intensive psychotherapy process, only one doctor should be involved. In general, the prescribing physician should play a helpful role by focusing heavily on the maintenance of the medication and seeing the patient more regularly only if a mental crisis or when changing medications. The main therapist should be the person to deal with the crises that may arise during psychotherapy. In cases where the patient cannot communicate with the therapist , it is not proper to look at the psychiatrist as a remedy. This is the case even if the therapist is unavailable for any other reason. Members of the treatment team need to regularly communicate and share relevant information with each other to supply a continuing context for interventions and changes in therapy . As with any psychopharmacological treatment, problems of non-compliance with the pharmaceutical regimen, such as overuse, underuse and/or covert use of other drugs or alcohol, should always be considered in any psychopharmacological treatment. For a complete and correct description, it may be necessary to have a working understanding of DID therapeutic procedures and to interact with the DID alternative identity system throughout the investigation of suspected non-compliance.

psychopharmacologist is not experienced in dealing with such questions, the primary therapist may manage performing this task. The same drug can cause various reactions in the individual suffering from dissociative identity disorder (DID). This may be due to various levels of physiological activation present in different identities, somatoform symptoms that can realistically mimic the adverse effects of all known drugs, and/or subjective experiences of identities being different from one another rather than different from one another.

6. Intended Symptoms of Medications

In general, the only time drugs have a chance to treat their intended symptoms is when they are reported on a "whole person." Patients with dissociative identity disorder often experience day-to-

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day changes in their symptoms ; this can be attributed to the modulation of dissociation defenses, as well as to the patients' individual predicament and stressors in their lives. It is therefore extremely helpful to pay attention to the general "emotional climate" of the patient's presentation when changing or adjusting medications. Rather than trying to treat the daily psychological changes in the " weather" , it is preferable to deal with the general "emotional climate" of the patient. It is possible that competent psychotherapy skills training in emotion control, anchoring, and management of PTSD and dissociative symptoms may be more successful than medicine in treating these conditions. Certain groupings of alternative identities, or certain alternative identities themselves, may have a feeling of "blocking" or "overriding" the effects of medicine. This can take various forms, such as when the basic physiological states of identities become more active, the basic agitation of identities increases because of intensifying internal conflict or persecution, or any combination of these factors. Similarly, identities can "deceive" other identities by either not taking medication or by taking more than the prescribed amount, and as a result, other identities willing to stick to their medication regimen experience amnesia for these behaviors. Similarly, identities can "fool" other identities by not taking medication or by taking more than the prescribed amount. Additionally, because of the hypnotic separation logic, some people with dissociative identity disorder may take excessive amounts of medication because they are under the impression that each of their other identities needs a dose of medication for a "separate body."

In most cases, it is most helpful to consider drugs for DID in the role of "shock absorbers" rather than therapeutic approaches. Patients suffering from DID and other complex forms of post-traumatic disorder may have only a partial response to various treatments. Therefore, prescribers need to have a high awareness of the possible side effects that may result from the use of many drugs in this patient group. When a crisis occurs, the psychiatrist may decide to change the dosage of the patient's medication. In many cases, this is both more cost-effective and more beneficial than starting new drug trials. Patients diagnosed with DID, like patients diagnosed with other conditions, need to be thoroughly evaluated for the risks and advantages of using medication, as well as the dangers of discontinuing medications and the need for adherence to treatment regimens. As with all patients, changes in stable and ancillary medications should be made carefully, ideally

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when the patient is not during a crisis or immersed in therapy and symptoms reappear. When the patient is more stable in the later stages of treatment, the patient, the psychiatrist on medication, and the primary therapist should be collaborative around issues of continuing or dropping medication. This is especially important when the patient is nearing the end of treatment. Unfortunately, there has been no systematic research on drugs to treat DID, and very few studies of pharmacotherapy for PTSD have shown it to be effective. Pharmaceutical therapy for dissociative identity disorder (DID) will continue to depend almost entirely on empirical and clinical experience until a stronger scientific basis is established.

7. Useful of Hypnosis in Psychotherapy

Its Role as a Tool Since the early 19th century, hypnosis has been used as an adjunct to the treatment of dissociative disorders (Ellenberger, 1970). There is a great deal of research focusing on the use of hypnosis for the treatment of DID (see Ross & Norton, 1989a). The use of hypnotic techniques as a complementary therapy choice for dissociative identity disorder (DID) is supported by several compelling arguments. First, individuals with dissociative identity disorder are more hypnotizable than patients in other clinical groups (Frischholz, Lipman, Braun, & Sachs, 1992). More hypnotizability when hypnosis is used is associated with an increased chance of therapeutic success. Second, hypnotic work has the potential to improve many different treatment approaches. Studies have shown that hypnosis is clinically effective in treating post-traumatic symptomatology (Cardea, Maldonado et al., 2009), and hypnosis-facilitated interventions have played a key role in the successful treatment of many DID patients. (RP Kluft, 1984, 1986, 1993a, 1994). Third, therapeutic treatment with this group of highly hypnotizable patients will always involve some form of hypnosis, since hypnosis can be in the form of spontaneous trance, autohypnosis, or heterohypnosis (trance created by another person; H. Spiegel & Spiegel, 1978, 2004).

dissociative patients to practice spontaneous hypnosis and some control over self-hypnosis may allow them to control certain distressing symptoms and use their hypnotic abilities to ease constructive self-care strategies. One formulation of this problem is that dissociative patients use

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various self-hypnosis strategies in an uninvited, uncontrolled, and unregulated way, often without realizing it. DID therapy have found a place for a variety of treatments that depend on the DID patient's self-hypnotic abilities; these techniques can be used with or without formal trance induction (RP Kluft , 1982, 1988a, 1989, 1994; Phillips & Frederick, 1995). These techniques include access to alternative identities that are not at once available, an intervention that can ease the emergence of identities important to the therapeutic process, and/or help resolve the situation of having an infantile, confused, or dysfunctional identity. "stuck" at the end of this therapy session. A similar strategy, known as restructuring, involves "reorganizing" a system of alternative identities that is in a dysfunctional state of disequilibrium.

This is done by proposing that various identities take on important roles within a safer and more stable constellation. Other hypnotherapeutic techniques are designed to modulate affect , explore and resolve disturbing psychological problems, control flashbacks and processing of reactions and traumatic memories, and control flashbacks and processing of interruptions and traumatic memories. For example, during Stage 2 (which deals with the treatment of traumatic memories), hypnotic methods such as internally portraying memories on a controllable screen can help regulate and modulate the impact of the memory on the person. "Split-screen" techniques can help with cognitive restructuring of traumatic events, and judicious use of regression techniques (keeping in mind the difficulties of memory) can be helpful when recalling past events. This can be conducted, for example, by rehearsing probable future events in a way that prevents relapse (Cardea , Maldonado , et al., 2009).

Because people with DID are capable of self-hypnosis, many hypnotic modalities can be used successfully throughout DID treatment, even when formal trance induction is not needed. Patients may be instructed to use at least some of these strategies outside of the therapist 's office, which is an advantage. In Phase One of Treatment, autohypnotic techniques can be particularly helpful to supply relaxation, allow the patient to use an imaginary safe place to soothe himself , alleviate various symptoms , aid dysphoric moods using ego-strengthening suggestions . supplying better coping skills, active awake hypnosis, etc. to create the ability to "ground" the present time using These techniques can also help relieve a variety of symptoms . In later stages, added autohypnotic

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skills can be taught. Some examples of these skills include the ability to have traumatic memories and the use of an internally visualized location as a "meeting place" that enables identities to discuss and problem-solve problems and everyday concerns. Clinicians should be aware of current issues about the use of hypnosis in trauma treatment, particularly the use of hypnosis-facilitated procedures to examine regions of forgetfulness or to further explore fragmented pictures or memories of the traumatic event (D. Brown et al ., 1998). Authorities supporting the use of hypnosis for these indications point to the recovery of material confirmed later (RP Kluft , 1995), as well as the therapeutic progress often achieved using hypnotic techniques. Some people believe that doing memory work while under the influence of hypnosis will make the patient more likely to confuse an imaginary memory with a real memory. However, the negative clinical outcomes attributed to hypnosis are most likely due to the use of misleading cues and other inappropriate practices of hypnosis rather than the hypnotic technique as a treatment modality. According to a study published by Scoboria , Mazzoni , and Kirsch (2006), memory distortions may not be caused by hypnosis itself, but by suggestive interventions such as leading questions. This is especially true for highly hypnotizable communities (McConkey , 1992). Like other therapies, hypnotherapy should only be used with proper training, both in the method itself and in its specific use in traumatized and dissociative patients. In addition to being highly hypnotizable, some DID patients are believed to be extremely fantasy -prone (Lynn , Rhue , & Green , 1988). (Lynn , Rhue and Green , 1988). A minority may be so, but many studies imply that most DID patients are only prone to fantasy in one way or another (Williams, Loewenstein , & Gleaves , 2004). (Williams, Loewenstein and Gleaves , 2004).

8. The Situation Regardless of Whether Hypnosis Is Induced or Not

Regardless of whether hypnosis is induced or not, there is a concern that at least some DID patients are prone to confuse fantasy with the real memory and/or confuse experiences that occur in the inner worlds of personalities with events that occur outside. This is the case regardless of whether hypnosis is induced or not (RP Kluft , 1998). Therefore, therapists who use hypnosis in an exploratory way should limit the number of leading questions they ask and avoid cues and

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pressures that have the potential to distort the characteristics of what is remembered while under the influence of hypnosis. Hypnosis may also leave patients an unwarranted level of confidence in those recalled in hypnotic situations, although there is evidence that giving specific informed consent on this latter issue can reduce this overconfidence (see Cardea , Maldonado , et al., 2009). If a therapist plans to use hypnosis or any other specialized technique with a patient, they must obtain proper informed consent from the patient beforehand. This approval should cover the potential benefits, risks, and limitations of the technique in question, as well as ongoing discussions of the technique. Informed consent should also include possible restrictions on the admissibility of testimony in legal settings regarding memories obtained under hypnosis. These restrictions should be based on laws and judgments in the authority in which the therapist practices and should be applied to memories obtained under hypnosis (American Society of Clinical Hypnosis, 1994).

9. EMDR

"EMDR is an acronym for eye movement desensitization and reprocessing." ("Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing (EMDR)") It was first set up in 1989 and has since gained popularity for its ability to accelerate the resolution of traumatic memories in patients with uncomplicated PTSD (Shapiro , 1989) . However, early use of standard EMDR for patients with unrecognized DID has resulted in serious clinical problems such as unintended violations of resolution barriers, overflow, sudden emergence of undiagnosed alternative identities, and rapid destabilization. These problems led to several serious clinical complications (Lazrove & Fine , 1996; Paulsen , 1995; Shapiro , 1995; Young, 1994). As a result of this, practitioners are now strongly encouraged to evaluate each client for the presence and degree of dissociation before beginning any EMDR therapy , regardless of the nature of the current problem. Additionally, the current consensus among experts is that the original EMDR protocols need to be changed to be used both safely and effectively in DID patients (Beere , 2009; Fine , 2009; Forgash & Knipe , 2008; Gelinas , 2003; Paulsen , 2008; Twombly , 2005; Van der Hart et al., 2006). EMDR in the treatment of DID offers several opportunities for positive outcomes. Among them is a consistent set of manual procedures for changing trauma-based distortions in one's self-representation , with

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Journal of Trauma & Dissociation , 12:115–187, 2011, developing relational bonds . :20 on October 21, 2011, Journal of Trauma & Dissociation , 12:115–187, 2011 159 Facilitating the Integration of Processed Traumatic Material into Alternative Identities (Fine , 2009; Gelinás , 2003; Twombly , 2005).

EMDR is useful in the formation of new behaviors because it allows people to process their earlier traumatic experiences and current triggers, then they can create new templates for desired skills or behaviors. This speeds up the process. A General Guide to the EMDR Dissociative Disorders Task Force and published in Shapiro (1995, 2001) EMDR's use in the dissociative Several suggestions can be found at Disorders . The guideline recommends integrating EMDR therapy into a comprehensive treatment plan rather than using it alone as a sole treatment option .

10. Conclusion

Only clinicians familiar with the treatment of dissociative disorders should use EMDR procedures and only after evaluating the patient's readiness for EMDR processing of traumatic material. (“dissociative disorder unit - Traduction en français - exemples anglais ...”) If a dissociative disorder is present, only clinicians familiar with the treatment of dissociative disorders should use EMDR procedures . EMDR processing should be considered only when the patient is generally stable and has adequate coping skills, adequate internal cooperation between alternative identities, and the ability to maintain the dual awareness focus required in EMDR procedures (Forgash & Knipe , 2008; Gelinás , 2003; Lazrove & Fine , 1996). ; Paulsen , 1995; Twombly , 2005). Contraindications to the use of eye movement desensitization and reprocessing include continued abusive relationship(s), strong resistance to processing from other identities, and major comorbid disorders such as psychosis, active drug abuse, or severe character dysfunction . An adjuvant method such as modified EMDR may be useful in the treatment of dissociative identity disorder (DID). Paulsen (1995), Lazrove and Fine (1996), and Twombly (2000) introduced concepts on how EMDR could be used in the treatment of dissociative disorders. Fine and Berkowitz (2001) presented an innovative phase-oriented model that uses the high hypnotizability of the DPD patient

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to change hypnotherapeutic and modified EMDR techniques. This makes it possible to safely manage and combine the traumatic material while the patient is permanently stabilized. When and where proper, modified EMDR procedures embedded in the general phase-oriented framework can be used to work on specific traumatic material. This has the potential to reduce the risks of early exposure to and overactivation of traumatic memories (Fine and Berkowitz , 2001; Forgash and Knipe , 2008; Gelinias , 2003; Paulsen , 2008; Twombly , 2005). The Phase-Focused Approach Training Manual (Shapiro , 2009), published by the EMDR Institute, has been updated to include a variety of EMDR interventions for each of the three phases. Clinicians have adopted EMDR interventions for symptom reduction and limitation, ego empowerment, working with alternative identities, and, where proper, consent negotiation for altered EMDR processing of traumatic memories, and the preparation of alternative identities.

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